

Policy

of Berdyansk State Pedagogical University on the Use of AI in Research

Approved by the Academic Council of Berdyansk State Pedagogical University,
Minutes No. 2 of September 11, 2025

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into the academic environment, transforming the ways knowledge is obtained, processed, and disseminated. The use of AI opens new opportunities for researchers – from analyzing large datasets and modeling complex processes to preparing scholarly texts and visualizations. At the same time, its application is accompanied by a number of challenges: risks to academic integrity, data confidentiality, intellectual property rights, equity of access, and environmental sustainability.

A key achievement in this field is the development of large language models (LLMs), a subset of AI designed to process and generate human-like text. LLMs serve as the foundation for generative artificial intelligence (GenAI), which specifically focuses on creating new content, including text and code, used in academic contexts. In this document, we use the term GenAI to denote systems capable of generating text, images, or code (e.g., ChatGPT, Claude, DeepSeek, Gemini, etc.). In contrast, we use AI when referring to artificial intelligence in a broader sense.

Berdyansk State Pedagogical University, as a participant in both national and international scientific communities and a member of the [Open4UA](#) consortium, recognizes the necessity of regulating practices related to the use of AI in research. This Policy aims to ensure a balance between the innovative potential of new technologies and the preservation of fundamental academic values: accountability, transparency, reproducibility, integrity, and public trust in science.

The Policy establishes the principles, rules, and mechanisms to be followed by the university's researchers and students when using AI in their research activities. It is based on international approaches to the responsible use of digital technologies, as well as the principles of open science and academic integrity.

The Policy is a framework document serving as the foundation for the development of detailed instructions, guidelines, recommendations, and procedures at the level of university departments.

2 Regulatory and Strategic Foundations of the Policy

This Policy has been developed in consideration of international and national framework documents that regulate the use of artificial intelligence, the safeguarding of academic integrity, and the development of open science.

International frameworks:

- UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2021).
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU Regulation 2016/679).
- European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act, 2024).
- European University Association declaration and action plan Universities without Walls: A Vision for 2030 (EUA, 2021).
- UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021).
- European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (2005).
- The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity adopted by ALLEA (2023).
- OECD AI Principles (2019; updated 2024).
- COPE Position Statement on Authorship and AI Tools (2023).

National frameworks (Ukraine):

- Constitution of Ukraine.
- Law of Ukraine On Education.
- Law of Ukraine On Higher Education.
- Law of Ukraine On Scientific and Scientific-Technical Activity.
- Law of Ukraine On Copyright and Related Rights.
- Law of Ukraine On the Protection of Personal Data.
- Law of Ukraine On Access to Public Information (No. 2939-VI, 2011).
- National Open Science Plan of Ukraine (2022).

3 Purpose and Core Principles

Purpose. To ensure the responsible, transparent, and safe use of AI in the University's research, to strengthen academic integrity, reproducibility, and public trust, and to enable the ethical integration of AI into the scientific process.

Principles

All actions of researchers when using AI must be guided by the following principles:

- **Accountability** – responsibility for research results always rests with the researcher; AI is not and cannot be an author or co-author.
- **Transparency** – the use of AI must be disclosed in a standardized form, indicating the tools, versions, and tasks performed.
- **Diligence** – AI-generated results must be critically reviewed by the researcher.
- **Integrity** – AI must not be used in ways that could undermine academic integrity or lead to fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism.
- **Confidentiality and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** – sensitive data, personal information, or restricted-access materials must not be transferred into uncontrolled AI services.
- **Fairness** – researchers acknowledge the presence of biases in AI models and prevent their reproduction or amplification in research.
- **Sustainability and Environmental Responsibility** – AI use must consider the principles of sustainable development: minimizing environmental and energy impacts, responsibly managing digital infrastructure, and ensuring the long-term social and ethical value of research.
- **Human Oversight and Control** – the researcher retains control of the process and the ability to intervene in or reject AI outputs.
- **Inclusion and Non-Discrimination** – AI must be applied in ways that do not create barriers or reinforce bias; assistive use is permitted to ensure equal opportunities.

4 SCOPE

This Policy applies to all staff, doctoral candidates, postgraduate researchers, students, visiting scholars, and contractors who conduct research on behalf of the University or using its resources. The Policy covers the entire research lifecycle (conceptualization, literature review, planning/methodology, data collection and analysis, modeling/computation, writing, verification, and dissemination of results).

5 Roles and Responsibilities

- **Heads of Departments/Units**
 - implement the Policy at the unit level;
 - organize training and awareness activities for staff and students;
 - approve and support local standard operating procedures.
- **Principal Investigators (PIs) / Project Leaders**
 - ensure compliance with the Policy within the scope of their project;
 - review the accuracy of AI contribution disclosure statements.
- **Researchers and Authors**
 - critically evaluate results obtained using GenAI;
 - prepare and submit AI contribution disclosure statements;
 - bear full responsibility for the accuracy, integrity, and legality of GenAI use.
- **Research Ethics Committee**
 - audits compliance with the Policy;
 - reviews and approves exceptions to the Policy's requirements;
 - provides guidance to researchers on ethical and legal aspects of AI use.

6 Transparency Requirements

General Principle of Transparency

All research outputs created with the use of artificial intelligence tools (manuscripts, abstracts, reports, grant applications, theses, etc.) must contain a clear and accessible explanation of the role of AI in the research. This explanation is a mandatory element of academic integrity and ensures public trust.

Recommended GAIDeT Standard

To unify and improve the quality of AI-use disclosure, the University recommends applying the [GAIDeT](#) (Generative AI Disclosure Taxonomy) framework through the GAIDeT Declaration Generator (<https://w3id.org/gaidet/>).

An AI contribution disclosure statement must include:

- identification of the tool(s) (name, version, date of use);
- description of the delegated tasks;
- confirmation of the authors' full responsibility and accountability.

If you use the GAIDeT standard in your research, please cite the following source:

Suchikova, Y., Tsybuliak, N., & Teixeira da Silva, J. A. & Nazarovets, S. (2025). GAIDeT (Generative AI Delegation Taxonomy): A taxonomy for humans to delegate tasks to generative artificial intelligence in scientific research and publishing. *Accountability in Research*, in press. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2025.2544331>

7 Unacceptable Use

The following are prohibited:

- ⊘ listing AI as an author or co-author;
- ⊘ uploading confidential, personal, or sensitive data into public models without risk assessment and adequate protection guarantees;
- ⊘ relying on AI outputs without critical verification;
- ⊘ disregarding requirements of ethics, safety, environmental responsibility, and intellectual property protection for the sake of expediency.
- ⊘ using GenAI to review/evaluate confidential materials (manuscripts, applications, reports) without explicit permission and without proper nondisclosure/data-processing agreements.

8 Competencies and Training

The University provides regular capacity-building programs on the ethical and responsible use of AI for students, researchers, project managers, members of ethics and expert boards, and data administrators.

Key provisions:

- **Basic competencies** in AI use (understanding how models work, recognizing bias risks, meeting transparency requirements) must be developed among all researchers and students engaged in scientific activity.
- **Advanced competencies** (data management, ethical aspects, development of local SOPs, compliance auditing) must be developed among project leaders, heads of structural units, ethics committee members, and data administrators.
- **Training formats** include seminars, workshops, online courses, and integration of modules into doctoral training programs and professional development programs for academic staff.
- **Systematic approach:** training is a continuous process and is updated in line with technological advances and international standards (AI Act, GDPR, UNESCO recommendations, etc.).

9 Key Risks and Mitigation Measures

The use of generative artificial intelligence is not without risks. Please consider the following limitations and ethical implications when using such tools:

- **Model stochasticity and risk of “hallucinations”**
Risk: results may be random, inconsistent, or contain fabricated data or references.
Mitigation: independent verification of key results; reproducing experiments with multiple methods; mandatory disclosure of model limitations in methodological sections.
- **Loss of reproducibility and transparency**
Risk: inability to reproduce results due to missing prompt logs, settings, or model versions.
Mitigation: creation and publication of “model/data cards”; preservation of code and data in open repositories under FAIR/CARE principles where feasible.
- **Violation of academic integrity**
Risk: the use of GenAI may lead to unintentional plagiarism, distorted citations, or hidden alterations of text.
Mitigation: use of pre-publication checklists, verification of text originality, reference accuracy, and inclusion of a GAIDeT disclosure statement.
- **Non-compliance with open science principles**
Risk: restricted access to data and methods prevents reproducibility and verification of results.

Mitigation: publication of methods, code, and data in open access (while respecting intellectual property and confidentiality requirements); use of institutional and international repositories.

10 Exceptions

Any deviations from this Policy must be documented in writing using the “AI Use Exception Request” form (indicating justification, duration, scope, risk assessment, and compensatory measures). The request is prepared by the PI/project leader or head of the unit and submitted to the Research Ethics Committee. Exceptions are only permitted upon the Committee’s approval.

11 Responsibility and Consequences of Violations

Violations of this Policy will result in disciplinary measures in accordance with the University’s internal regulations and/or the requirements of funders/journals (including rejection/withdrawal of works, restricted access to infrastructure, or temporary prohibition from project leadership). Violations may also lead to notification of publishers, sponsors, or government authorities.

The Research Ethics Committee may initiate an audit or internal investigation; such investigations must uphold the principles of impartiality, confidentiality, due process, and the right to explanation.